

Shaping Crisis Narratives: A Terminological - Ontological Analysis of Twitter Discourse on the Moria Refugee Camp

Abstract

This study examines the terminology and ontological structures underpinning online discourse about the Moria refugee camp on Twitter. By analyzing a corpus of 29,992 English tweets (2016–2020) using Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) for topic modeling, this study aims to identify how terms such as “*asylum seekers*” and “*EU*” are used to frame the refugee crisis. Findings reveal evolving patterns in terminology, with shifts reflecting real-world events such as the COVID-19 pandemic and the 2020 camp fire. The topic modeling results categorize discourse into key themes and actors, highlighting how these elements interact to shape public perceptions and policy debates. This research contributes to understanding the role of terminology in crisis narratives and demonstrates how ontological frameworks can provide valuable insights into the dynamics of online discourse on migration.

1. Introduction

The discourse surrounding refugee encampment is shaped not only by political and humanitarian concerns but also by the terminology used to frame it (Turner, 2015). Public debates on migration and asylum are increasingly taking place on digital platforms, particularly Twitter, where individuals, organizations, and policymakers engage in discussions, mobilize support, and shape narratives (Mahabir et al., 2018; Nerghes & Lee, 2019). This study examines how key terms, conceptual categories, and discursive shifts have shaped online discussions about the Moria refugee camp, one of the most controversial sites of European migration management.

The Moria camp, officially known as the Moria Reception and Identification Centre, was Europe’s largest refugee camp (Gordon & Larsen, 2021), housing thousands of asylum seekers. The destructive fire of September 2020 marked a turning point for the Moria refugee camp, triggering a notable shift in the way the camp was discussed online. This event not only intensified debates on migration policies but also altered the terminology and conceptual framing of encampment, responsibility, and refugee rights in digital spaces.

This paper investigates how public discourse on Twitter has structured, classified, and framed key concepts related to Moria over time. Using a dataset of 29,992 English-language tweets from January 2016 to December 2020, topic modeling and terminology analysis are employed to examine the evolving vocabulary, dominant themes, and conceptual classifications that emerged in online discussions. The study seeks to address the following questions:

- How has the terminology and conceptual framing of the Moria refugee camp evolved on Twitter?
- What are the dominant thematic structures and semantic networks present in discussions about Moria?
- How do shifts in terminology correlate with real-world events such as the COVID-19 crisis and the Moria fire?

By focusing on the linguistic and ontological dimensions of discourse, this study contributes to a broader understanding of how migration-related terminology is shaped, contested, and repurposed in digital spaces.

2. Methodology

2.1 Corpus Compilation

For the purposes of this study, a corpus of tweets discussing the Moria camp was compiled, using sncrape to collect historical data spanning from January 2016 to December 2020. Given that no existing social media dataset specifically focuses on the terminology of refugee encampment, this dataset represents a unique resource for analyzing linguistic and conceptual patterns in this context.

The corpus consists of 29,992 English-language tweets containing the keyword “Moria camp”, extracted from an initial dataset of 33,237 tweets. The selection of English tweets ensures a consistent linguistic framework for terminology analysis. The dataset includes metadata such as timestamps and hashtags, allowing for an examination of terminological shifts over time.

Hashtags, in particular, provide insight into emergent terminology and conceptual classifications used by different actors in the discourse. The most frequent hashtags in the dataset include #moria, #moriacamp, #greece, #lesvos, #refugees, #covid19, and #leavenoonebehind, reflecting key thematic and terminological associations.

2.2 Analytical Approach

To analyze the terminological and thematic structures in the dataset, topic modeling and terminology extraction techniques are deployed and they are described in the subsections below in more detail.

2.2.1 Topic Modeling

Topic modeling enables the identification of dominant themes and evolving terminological patterns within large text datasets (Liu, 2020). For the topic modeling analysis, Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) (Blei et al., 2003) is used to extract key topics from the corpus, allowing the identification of recurring lexical structures and co-occurring terms, as well as the tracking of changes in thematic emphasis over time and the mapping of the evolution of key conceptual domains in Moria-related discourse.

2.2.2 Terminology Extraction & Conceptual Mapping

Beyond topic modeling, terminology extraction methods are applied as well, in order to examine how key terms are structured and interrelated within the discourse. With this method, it is possible to identify core terminologies associated with Moria (e.g., “refugee crisis,” “humanitarian disaster,” “detention center”), conceptual shifts over time, including emerging and declining terms, and thematic networks, linking terms to broader ontological categories related to migration, policy, and humanitarianism.

2.2.3 Data Preprocessing

To ensure consistency in terminology analysis, standard text preprocessing techniques are applied, including lowercasing (to unify term variations), punctuation and stop-word removal to eliminate

noise, and finally custom stop-word filtering for the exclusion of high-frequency but non-informative terms like “https” and “t.co”.

3. Results

3.1 Topic Modeling and Terminology Extraction

Using Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), nine distinct topics were identified in the Twitter discourse surrounding the Moria refugee camp. The optimal number of topics was determined based on perplexity and coherence scores (*Perplexity: -7.61; Coherence: 0.39*). These topics represent recurring terminologies and conceptual structures associated with Moria-related discussions.

Table 1: Topics found via LDA

Topic #0	moria camp refugee asylum refugees seekers lesbos island greek greece
Topic #1	support please working moria camp situation people give almost died
Topic #2	moria camp refugee inside doctor moriacamp living story hell europe
Topic #3	camp moria greece refugee lesbos refugees fire people coronavirus island
Topic #4	outbreak moria camp social distancing arrivals refugee bbcworld covid moriacamp
Topic #5	moria camp refugees lesbos eu people moriacamp refugee greece camps
Topic #6	evacuation call urgent camp moria change petition fire sign radical
Topic #7	sosmoria commission dangerously beach camp moria online highlight protesting colleague
Topic #8	die steps worry tear injured gas warning donating moria fundraiser

Table 1 provides an overview of the nine topics and their key lexical components:

- Topic 0: *Encampment Terminology* – Keywords related to refugee life, including “camp,” “asylum,” and “Lesbos.”
- Topic 1: *Humanitarian Appeals* – Terminology linked to calls for aid, featuring terms like “support,” “help,” and “crisis.”
- Topic 2: *Narratives & Testimonies* – Personal accounts and thematic terms like “doctor,” “child,” and “conditions.”
- Topic 3: *Major Events & Crises* – Discussion of specific crises, particularly the Moria fire and COVID-19 outbreak.
- Topic 4: *COVID-19 and Public Health* – Discourse around “social distancing,” “outbreak,” and “quarantine.”
- Topic 5: *Policy & Geopolitical Context* – Keywords referencing the European Union and migration policies.

- Topic 6: *Evacuation and Advocacy* – Terms related to activism, such as “petition” and “evacuate.”
- Topic 7: *Digital Activism & Awareness* – Thematic terms linked to online campaigns and hashtag activism.
- Topic 8: *Fundraising & Humanitarian Support* – Lexical patterns in discussions on donations and relief efforts.

These findings illustrate how specific terminology clusters dominate discussions about Moria camp, reflecting both pragmatic concerns (e.g., evacuation, humanitarian aid) and broader geopolitical narratives (e.g., EU policies, migration crisis).

Fig.1 Intertopic distance in 2D space

Fig. 1 visualizes the intertopic distance using multidimensional scaling. The clear separation of topic clusters suggests that the themes in Moria-related discourse are well-defined and non-overlapping, reinforcing the distinct conceptual domains that structure public discussions.

Additionally, lexical pattern analysis was conducted to extract the most frequent bigrams and trigrams within each topic. Table 2 presents the top 10 bigrams, highlighting key phrase structures such as “fire Moria” and “urgent evacuation,” which correspond to high-impact events.

Table 2: Top 10 most common bigrams

Count	
11023	moria camp
8215	refugee camp
5908	moria refugee
5395	camp moria
2357	fire moria
1879	camp lesbos
1651	island lesbos
1639	camp lesvos
1466	urgent evacuation
1455	radical change

Similarly, Table 3 showcases the most common trigrams, emphasizing emergency-related discourse (e.g., “radical change petition,” “help Moria refugees”). These multi-word expressions provide deeper insights into how terminology is formed, contextualized, and mobilized within digital discourse.

Table 3: Top 10 most common trigrams

Count	
5812	moria refugee camp
1875	fire moria camp
1434	evacuation radical change
1434	urgent evacuation radical
1431	call urgent evacuation
1422	moria camp call
1421	camp call urgent
1156	radical change sign

Table 3: Top 10 most common trigrams

1155	change sign petition
1008	moria camp lesvos

3.2 Conceptual Evolution of Moria-Related Terminology

To understand how terminology and thematic structures evolve over time, the temporal distribution of key terms and topics is analyzed. The following patterns have been uncovered:

- Shifts in dominant terminologies: Early discussions (2016–2018) predominantly used “asylum seekers” and “refugee crisis,” whereas post-2020 discourse shifted towards “humanitarian disaster” and “fire Moria.” This shift indicates a discursive transition from a policy-focused debate to crisis-driven terminology.
- Event-driven lexical peaks: Major events such as the COVID-19 pandemic and Moria camp fire triggered spikes in specific terminologies. For instance, “quarantine” and “social distancing” appeared prominently in early 2020, while “emergency evacuation” and “burned camp” dominated the discourse following the September 2020 fire.
- Thematic convergence and divergence: While policy-oriented discourse (e.g., Topic 5) remained relatively stable, activist terminology (Topics 6 & 7) gained prominence post-2019.

These findings underscore the dynamic nature of terminology in humanitarian discourse, illustrating how real-world crises shape linguistic patterns and conceptual framing in digital spaces.

4. Discussion

This section interprets the findings presented in Section 3, analyzing how terminological structures in Twitter discourse about the Moria camp have evolved in response to historical events and societal dynamics. Each research question is addressed through the lens of lexical shifts, conceptual framing, and event-driven discourse formation.

RQ1: How has public discourse on the Moria camp changed on Twitter?

The topic modeling analysis identified key thematic lexical clusters reflecting the evolution of Twitter discourse. Initial discussions (2016–2018) focused on descriptive narratives related to refugee conditions, employing terminology such as “*asylum seekers*,” “*humanitarian crisis*,” and “*EU response*.” However, as the crisis escalated, discourse shifted towards activist and urgency-driven terminology, exemplified by bigrams like “*emergency evacuation*,” “*Moria fire*,” and the trigram “*radical change petition*.”

Two major terminological shifts were observed:

1. Event-driven lexical reconfiguration: The Moria camp fire (2020) and COVID-19 pandemic introduced new terminology clusters: “*social distancing*,” “*quarantine measures*,” and “*burned camp*.”
2. Increasing digital activism and advocacy: Post-2019, a rise in activist-driven discourse was observed, characterized by terms like “*petition*,” “*EU failure*,” and “*justice for refugees*.” This indicates a transition where Twitter became a site of political mobilization.

RQ2: What is the overall topic structure and conceptual tone of Moria-related discourse?

The intertopic analysis (Fig. 1) confirmed distinct and non-overlapping thematic clusters, suggesting that discussions on Moria camp were structured around well-defined conceptual domains. Core lexical structures remain intact yet adapting to new socio-political contexts.

From a conceptual standpoint, discourse can be categorized into three overarching domains:

1. Humanitarian and living conditions: Focused on *refugee life, medical aid, and support appeals*.
2. Crisis events and urgency discourse: Emerging during critical events, using terms like “*fire emergency*,” “*evacuate now*,” and “*COVID outbreak*.”
3. Policy and geopolitical narratives: Highlighting the EU’s role in refugee management, employing terms such as “*border policies*” and “*migrant crisis*.”

RQ3: How do these discourse shifts align with historical events?

The evolution of Moria-related terminology correlates closely with major geopolitical and humanitarian developments:

- 2016–2018: Descriptive discourse dominates, focusing on e.g. “*refugee crisis*.”
- 2019–2020: Crisis lexicon emerges, introducing terms like “*COVID outbreak*,” “*fire evacuation*,” and “*humanitarian failure*.”

Throughout 2020, advocacy and activism discourse intensifies, with an increase in calls for action, e.g. “change sign petition” , “radical change sign”.

5. Conclusion

This study examined the terminological and conceptual evolution of Twitter discourse surrounding the Moria refugee camp. Findings reveal that public discourse is shaped by real-world crises, policy shifts, and digital activism, with distinct lexical shifts occurring during critical events such as the Moria camp fire and COVID-19 outbreak.

From a terminology perspective, this analysis highlights how event-driven discourse reconfigures conceptual structures, introducing new terminology clusters while maintaining core thematic domains. The transition from descriptive narratives (e.g., *asylum seekers, humanitarian crisis*) to activist-driven discourse (e.g., *emergency evacuation, radical change*) underscores the adaptive nature of online discourse.

By exploring Twitter as a site of terminological evolution, this study contributes to a broader understanding of migration discourse in digital spaces. Future research could further explore cross-linguistic variations, the role of algorithmic amplification, and the interplay between social media and policy framing.

References

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